

USEFUL INSTRUCTIONAL STRATEGIES IN IMPROVEMENT OF SPEAKING SKILLS FOR ENGLISH LEARNERS

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Annotation: This article is aimed to prepare students to be more self-confident while speaking in different real life contexts regardless of repetitive oral practices and student-student cooperation. In this activity, Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) is used clearly. Its objective is mainly to teach oral proficiency to produce learners who can communicate intelligibly by using grammatical rules and learners can answer with actions as well as approaches.

Keywords: techniques, entertaining, approaches, procedures, phase, critical thinking, self-confidence, self-efficacy, deficiency, unmotivated, inquisitive strategies, assessment, |CLT, think-pair-share, accuracy, fluency.

Instructional strategies play a crucial role in enhancing speaking skills among language learners. One effective strategy is providing ample opportunities for students to engage in meaningful conversations and discussions. This can be achieved through pair work, group discussions, debates, and role-playing activities. Another useful approach is to incorporate real-life scenarios and authentic materials into the lessons, allowing students to practice speaking in context. Additionally, teachers can provide constructive feedback and error correction to help students improve their pronunciation, fluency, and accuracy. Encouraging students to use a variety of speaking strategies, such as paraphrasing, asking for clarification, and expressing opinions, can also contribute to their overall speaking proficiency. By employing a combination of these instructional strategies, educators can create a dynamic and interactive learning environment that fosters the development of strong speaking skills in language learners. According to the Jeff Stranks "it is necessary to demonstrate activities for adolescents that not only encourage to learn but also develop their critical thinking abilities and good materials help teachers to do this" (p.29). As an ESL instructor, our major goal is to direct their enthusiasm and drive toward language study and, ideally, proficiency. Therefore, it is difficult to increase adolescents' interest in learning a language and can be difficult to keep their attention while explaining topics. However, it is possible to do so by using entertaining techniques and activities to draw students' attention. Clement et al. (1994) argues that "the applicability of the self-confidence is also a significant motivational subsystem in foreign language learning situations, in which there is

little direct contact with members of the L2 community but considerable indirect contact with the L2 culture through the media, for example, as is the case with world languages such as English". In this lack of investment, teacher force students to speak more in L2 language and organize speaking activities, debates or discussions which can help students to produce their communicative language. Also her self-efficacy is low and sometimes focus on mistakes and deficiencies she had rather than concentration on performing successful tasks. Norton & Toohey (2001) argues that " the language learner, despite being highly motivated, may not be invested in the language practices of a given classroom. The learner could then be excluded from those practices, or choose not to participate in classroom activities. In time, the learner could be positioned as a 'poor' or unmotivated language learner by others". So, in this position, teachers' role is important and should encourage student with interesting contents and continually praising them for their efforts. When learners affective filter is high, this is due to their investment in the target language which will lead them to speak. Also, no any teacher or instructor can inspire students to study hard if they are unmotivated and there is a proverb that "you can make a horse water but you can't make him drink". So that's why, any materials and techniques which can help them to improve self-confidence and efficacy have to be prepared beforehand. During lessons, Instructors should manage how to handle students with interesting lesson plans and activities. One of them can be Eternal Mingle activity which is really helpful for students oral communication skills. Students will be able to use new vocabulary in their speech with the help of various approaches. Picture demonstration will widen their outlook. They will be able to comprehend and apply in speech the given information. In this way, students will be able to increase active attendance of the pupils during the activity through interesting information as well as inquisitive strategies. At the end of the lesson students could be able to discuss looking into some pictures and they can make some short stories using new words. When it comes to learning phase and procedure, this activity can be acted in while task to improve students' awareness in both communication and grammar. Students can do this activity as a practice stage to consolidate some topics related to the grammatical and lexical with speaking during the lesson. After learning all features of tenses, it would be great to use from this activity with the help of speaking to identify whether students understand or not. Teacher asks about grammatical tenses as a consolidation from students. They try to use these tenses in both affirmative, negative and question form in their answer. In While-speaking activity, Teacher

hands out a slip of paper to each students owing to write their own questions. Then, Students should write two questions including different grammatical tenses. After that, students change their place and walk around until they find someone to talk. They can ask questions from any classmates they want using range of vocabularies. Then, teacher also join to the group and try to answer and get to know students. After being asked two questions, they also exchange their questions with others to respond and define their thoughts. At least one student should answer six different questions and make a speech with different partners to hear different pronunciation. As a post-speaking activity, students will be shown how to use the platform “Grammarly” owing to correct their grammar mistakes. This makes sure everything they type is easy to read, effective, and mistake-free. In this activity, students firstly work individually, then after making questions, they work in pairs and with a whole group. With the help of this task they have a great opportunity to interact with their classmates and exchange their ideas and give some feedback. Instructional Strategies play a major role in teaching learners effectively. While doing this task, some classroom instructional strategies are focused to make the lesson more engaging and comprehensible. Students in this activity, mostly use Think-pair-share strategies, they firstly work alone and then work with in pairs and whole groups. Also they utilize alternative rotation strategies while they are exchanging their partners after being questioned. Finally, prompting and chunking can be also done if there are some misunderstandings or mistakes among students.

Assessment part is also highly demanded in this activity because students are able to take more feedbacks and correct their mistakes. This activity improves students participation and helps teacher to realize who is active and who is passive. By interacting with each students while questioning, teacher also know their mistakes and pronunciation skills and then give feedback them. Students can be assessed according to their fluency, accuracy, grammar and lexical structure and the meaning. Some students are good enough to explain their thoughts with wide range of vocabularies, but others can have difficulties with word structure, intonation and pronunciation. Doing engaging activities in speaking courses is really handful to interact and draw all students attention. Also, teacher should never stop to learn new comprehensive pedagogies which can help learners intellectually and emotionally. According to Featherstone (1993), “the new teacher is constantly on stage and urgently needs to develop a performing self with whom he or she can live comfortably” (p.101). The main reason that I opted for is that, I myself use this communicative task during my

speaking lessons. Because, in one section students can consolidate some topics related to grammar and lexical. Some of my students have lack of knowledge in grammar rules and how to use them correctly in speech even if they speak fluently. Fortunately, with the help of this activity teachers can easily enhance students speaking with gradual revision of grammar. Also, students can work collaboratively and listen each other, discuss their ideas and eventually, it ensures a high level of student participation and understanding more deeper. So such valuable speaking activities challenge and inspire students to use words and phrases and grammatical structures when they are expressing their thoughts. As an addition, leaning on ideas of Hall Houston, students get tired of the same sitting and it is really efficient to make movements with giving more energy to learn the language perfectly. Larsen-Freeman (2003) documents that “the conversation is a particularly good way in which to raise consciousness because, since learners generated the interaction, they are invested in it”. Learners also try to communicate with each other in this task and they have great opportunity to make physical-linguistic connections and community building. Absolutely, learners can share ideas, information by describing their mind and outlook. This speaking activity is aimed to prepare students to be more self-confident while speaking in different real life contexts regardless of repetitive oral practices and student-student cooperation. Felder and Henriquez (1995) argue that “In order to implement CLT methods successfully, it requires more than simply placing students into pairs and groups”. Accordingly, Students work in think-pair-share position and they have more chances to communicate and exchange ideas of each other. As an extra, in post stage, teacher gives test link from Kahoot owing to improve the comprehension of tenses and not to make mistakes while communicating in their speech.

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